

Inclusion Criteria

- Healthy adults aged 18-55 (inclusive, at the time of consent)
- Fluent spoken English – to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the research project
- Capacity to provide written informed consent in English
- Females of childbearing potential with a negative urine pregnancy test at screening and willing to practice adequate contraceptive measures as per UK Clinical Trial Facilitation Group during the study
- Willing to provide their household contacts with the Close Contact Screening Information Letter
- For Phase C, RSV neutralizing antibody titre in the lowest 10th percentile of screened participants

Exclusion Criteria

- Research participant:
 - Currently involved in another study unless observational or non-interventional. Exceptions may be applied at the discretion of the Chief Investigator to ensure no harm comes to the participants (e.g. excessive blood sampling or nasal sampling)
 - Participated in a previous Spn6B EHPC study ≤ 3 years or an Spn3 EHPC study ≤ 1 year before screening
- Unable to travel to outpatient clinic for visits during phase B/C after RSV challenge (for up to 10 days or 7 days if negative for RSV) without using public transport.
- Unable to wear a fluid resistant surgical mask.
- Vaccination:
 - No live vaccination within four weeks prior to enrolment (defined as time of first inoculation)
 - Previous pneumococcal or (investigational) RSV vaccination (including in a research study)
- Allergy:
 - Allergy to beta-lactam antibiotics (including penicillin and amoxicillin)
- Medical history leading to increased risk of severe infection, illness including but not limited to:
 - Asplenia or dysfunction of the spleen
 - Chronic respiratory disease (e.g. asthma [requiring medication (including salbutamol inhaler) within last 12 months], COPD, bronchiectasis, and sleep apnoea)
 - Chronic heart disease (e.g. angina, ischaemic heart disease, chronic heart failure) – controlled and stable hypertension may be included
 - Chronic kidney disease (e.g. nephrotic syndrome, kidney transplant, requires dialysis)
 - Chronic liver disease (e.g. cirrhosis, biliary atresia, hepatitis)
 - Chronic neurological disease that limits mobility, bulbar or respiratory function (including stroke, Parkinson's disease, dementia, and multiple sclerosis)
 - Diabetes mellitus (including diet controlled)
 - Receipt of immunosuppressive therapy such as anti-cancer chemotherapy or radiation therapy within the preceding 12 months or long-term systemic corticosteroid, Roaccutane, or disease modifying anti-rheumatoid drugs therapy (for more than 7 consecutive days within the 3 months prior to enrolment)
 - Individuals with cochlear ear implants

- Individuals with major CSF leaks (e.g. following traumatic, major skull surgery, or requiring CSF shunts)
- Subjects with known or suspected immune deficiency (e.g. known IgA deficiency, immotile cilia syndrome, or Kartagener's syndrome)
- Autoimmune disease
- History of frequent nose bleeds
- Bleeding disorders
- Current medical issues
 - Acute URTI in the four weeks preceding recruitment
 - Any uncontrolled medical or surgical condition (e.g. mental health conditions, epilepsy, narcolepsy, or chronic pain) at the discretion of the study doctor
- Any major pneumococcal illness or pneumonia requiring hospitalization in the last 10 years
- Medication:
 - Any medication that may affect the immune system in the last 3 months (e.g. systemic steroids [IM/IV], Roaccutane, disease modifying anti-rheumatoid drugs)
 - Long-term antibiotic use
 - Recipient of monoclonal antibodies for any indication within one year of period at screening
 - Recipient of blood transfusion products within the last year
 - Any medication that may affect the coagulation system in the last 3 months (excluding aspirin)
 - Use of any medication or other product (prescription or over the counter) for symptoms of rhinitis or nasal congestion within the last 1 month
- Maternal:
 - Female participants who are pregnant.
 - Female participants who are lactating.
 - Female participants who intend to become pregnant during the study.
 - Female participants unable to take contraception measures during the study (from consent to final study visit at day 60)
- Direct caring role or share living accommodation with individuals at higher risk from infection:
 - Children under the age of 5 years.
 - Adults > 65 years old.
 - Adults with chronic ill health or immunosuppression.
 - Adults classified as clinically extremely vulnerable by the NHS
- Health-care worker
- Current or ex-smoker (regular cigarettes/cigars/e-cigarette/vaping/smoking of recreational drugs) in the last 6 months
- Previous significant smoking history (more than 5 cigarettes per day for 20 years or the equivalent [i.e. >5 pack years])
- Regularly drinks ≥ 3 units/day (male) or ≥ 2 units/day (female)
- Regularly uses recreational drugs
- Significant mental health disorders:
 - Uncontrolled condition or previous admission to a psychiatric unit (at the discretion of the research clinician) which would impair the participants ability to safely participate in the study

- Moderate or severe depression or anxiety as classified by the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Score at screening or challenge that is deemed clinically significant by the study doctors
- Overseas travel planned during 21-day period following first inoculation
- Participants FBC results do not meet the required criteria on screening bloods: HB <90 g/L, total WCC <1.5x10⁹/L, total WCC <12x10⁹/L and platelets <75x10⁹/L
- Any other issue which, in the opinion of the study staff, may:
 - Put the participant or their contacts at risk because of participation in the study.
 - Adversely affect the interpretation of the study results, or
 - Impair the participant's ability to participate in the study.

Temporary exclusion criteria on day of challenge

- Current acute infective illness – delay inoculation by 14 days
- Recent /current URTI – delay inoculation by 4 weeks after last day of illness.
- Asymptomatic positive COVID-19 OR *RSV-A swab (taken on day of planned challenge) – delay inoculation by 21 days.
- Antimicrobial (including antiviral) use – delay inoculation by 28 days from last date of antimicrobial therapy.
- Nasal carriage- participants who have natural pneumococcal carriage identified at screening will be excluded– delay until carriage clearance.

* For clarity, a participant who has a positive RSV-A swab at day 7 following primary RSV inoculation will proceed to second inoculation with Spn unless they meet individual stopping rule criteria or at investigator discretion.

List of inclusion and exclusion criteria including temporary exclusion criteria. EHPC: experimental human pneumococcal colonisation; COPD: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; CSF: cerebrospinal fluid; IM: intramuscular; IV: intravenous; FBC: full blood count; HB: haemoglobin; WCC: white cell count; URTI: upper respiratory tract infection